

IDION is a web-based MWE resource addressed to human users and to NLP. It contains about 2500 Modern Greek (EL) and 160 Pomak verb MWEs available under a CC-BY-NC license. Pomak is an endangered South East Slavic language variety (Thrace/Greece). We present the searches available to the user.

Lemma form, variants and lexical variants

A VMWE lemma form contains

- place-holders for the free dependants of the VMWE: free NPs, possessive pronouns, phrasal complements
- the lexicalised components (Savary et al. 2018): fixed forms or fixed lemma but not fixed form

Fixed lemma but not fixed form (instructions to the encoders):

- = the lemma form of the verb if all its inflectional paradigm is in usage
- = the form detected in the data and closer to the lemma when only a part of the inflectional paradigm of the verb is used
- = ethic genitives are in the third singular with the lemma form of the verb and otherwise in the third plural

A VMWE may have more than one lemma forms, or variants, due to orthographic variations, diminutives, optional appositions or adverbs, and ethic genitives

Lexical variants
 When the non-verbal fixed parts of two VMWEs with identical meaning differ from each other in terms of forms of content words

VMWEs which share their fixed parts and meaning but have a different verb are encoded as lexical variants and synonyms.

UD analysis of variants

The working examples

βάζω τη θηλειά γύρω από το λαιμό κάποιου
 I put the noose around from the neck of smb
 'to hold a gun to one's head'

χάνω τα αυγά και τα καλάθια
 I lose the eggs and the baskets
 'I lose control over a situation'

κάτι βγαίνει στο φως
 smth exits to the light
 'smth is brought to light'

Flexible usages-with representative usage examples

Synonyms (result of inferencing)

“Semantic proximity” as synonymy: a transitive relation
 Sets of synonymous VMWEs are dynamically generated: IDION infers that two expressions are “synonymous” even when their documentation does not contain this statement.
 The approach requires constant maintenance.

Overview of the semantic relations of a VMWE

Encoded relations between VMWEs: causative & non-causative, between VMWEs with the same fixed part and the equivalents of verbs “be” and “have” as heads, opposite, converse (e.g., VMWEs headed by buy and sell, verb alternation)

Intensifiers, Mitigators, Examples